

Colouring Cities: A network of open platforms to improve the availability of data on the building stock for research, government and society

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Abstract. This contribution presents the Colouring Cities Research Programme (CCRP) as an open network that provides accessible and standardized building data to support research relating to UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It facilitates collaboration and innovation and uses artificial intelligence and machine learning to enrich the data. The CCRP includes a global consortium of researchers, academic institutions that operate the open interactive Colouring Cities platforms. By sharing knowledge and resources, the CCRP accelerates research into buildings, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable future for all, with a focus on openness, transparency and societal engagement, enabling data-driven decision-making.

Submission Type. Project

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Keywords. Building stock, citizen science, participatory GIS, machine learning

1 Introduction

Any research, administrative or civil society activity related to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that involves geospatial analysis requires access to appropriate data. Access to fundamental information about buildings, including materials, age, and condition, is often lacking. However, having access to open, high-

quality, and standardized geospatial microdata on the building stock can significantly simplify the process of addressing SDG-relevant questions. By facilitating collaboration and leveraging the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), this data can ultimately lead to faster and more efficient solutions.

In the following sections, we present the Colouring Cities Research Programme (CCRP), an open data platform network providing accessible and standardized geospatial data, supporting Colouring Cities platforms, and driving cross-country discussion on current and future development perspectives.

2 Colouring Cities Research Programme (CCRP)

The Colouring Cities Research Programme (CCRP) is an informal, non-competitive research initiative that addresses issues with access, quality and reliability of spatial data relating to buildings, and built and green/blue infrastructure (Hudson, 2025). It comprises an informal consortium of international researchers who share an interest in open knowledge and resources, and in co-working on reproducible, open tools to accelerate SDG-related research at local, national, and global scales. By doing so, the CCRP aims to overcome common obstacles to collaboration within the academic community. The CCRP has been developed within academia over the past decade as a decentralised system and today engages academic institutions from over thirty countries which are grouped into six CCRP Global Hubs that help facilitate

co-working in line with CCRP protocols. Hubs that operate Colouring Cities platforms following CCRP protocols. Current operational Hubs cover North America, Europe, Middle East, Latin America, Africa, and Asia Pacific and both Asia Pacific and South/Southeast Asia.

At the core of the CCRP is a network of open-source national data platforms that facilitate knowledge collation and sharing of micro-spatial data on buildings, as well as built and blue-green infrastructure. CCRP academic partners independently manage national platforms but employ standard interfaces to collect, collate, standardise, verify, visualise and release spatial data. These platforms can integrate large-scale building datasets, such as the EUBUCCO dataset (Milojevic-Dupont et al., 2023), generated by harmonizing data from 50 open government datasets and OpenStreetMap, followed by validation to ensure the quality and consistency of building footprints and attributes. All CCRP code, data and methods are made available under open licences. Initially run by research groups interested in specific SDG-related research questions, CCRP platforms are designed to evolve incrementally into low-cost, permanent open national databases managed by academia and co-created with/used by government, non-profits, industry and citizens. The platforms are supported by CCRP Expert Data Groups, chaired by different countries, which are set up for each of the CCRP’s main data categories. Experts provide specialized guidance on specific data classes and formats, as well as security and privacy considerations. They collaboratively investigate data applications, while exploring the strategic integration of AI and ML in data analysis and modeling to drive informed decision-making and innovation. The CCRP also has an international technical group, developing CCRP features and plug-ins across countries, an impact section for case studies, and an informal operations group which oversees the CCRP GitHub open code repository, platform manuals and other core open resources.

The Colouring Cities Research Programme (CCRP) is supported by a global academic network of over 100 researchers from more than 30 countries (Fig. 1). It brings together a diverse range of multidisciplinary expertise, including computer science, data science, urban science, and environmental science. Key areas of focus include data ethics, AI/ML, and spatial data visualization.

3 Colouring Cities platforms

Each Colouring Cities platform features web-based, interactive map interface that enables the collaborative collection and visualization of building data, facilitating the gathering of over 150 classes of standardized spatial data, organized into twelve main categories. These categories capture information on current building attributes, such as location, land use, typology, size, materials/construction, and age, as well as long and short-term dynamic behavior, planning controls, building performance, building team and energy aspects, blue and green infrastructure context, and the extent of damage to buildings in disaster situations. Most data are standardized, but locally specific bespoke data can also be collected, provided the related open code is shared. Academic oversight prioritizes the ethical collection of data and the privacy and security of users and building occupiers in all aspects of CCRP design and operation. For example, the CCRP does not release data on the interiors of homes that could be deemed personal and does not link free text boxes to georeferenced building polygons. Specific trust models are being discussed within the CCRP to enable the secure collection and analysis of more sensitive data within academia.

Platforms are coded to integrate multiple methods of spatial data capture. The focus is on existing bulk uploads (moderated by academia), live/near-time data streamed from official APIs, new large-scale computationally inferred data, and crowdsourcing at the building level.

Figure 1. CCRP Global Academic Network (as of 2/ 2025) and the Colouring Cities platforms. (Source: <https://colouringcities.org/>)

Each method is designed to support specific stakeholder groups and maximize data quality, accuracy, and completeness. APIs, for example, are well-suited to stream government datasets, such as planning data, where frequent updates are necessary. Crowdsourcing data on a building-by-building basis is effective for local residents, schools, civic organizations, and local historians, as buildings colour as soon as data are added. Users are responsible for determining whether the data are fit for purpose and are provided with as much information as possible to assess data reliability. This includes information on data capturing methods, source links, and editing history (comparable to OpenStreetMap). Uncertainty quantification features are also planned.

4 Outlook

The Colouring Cities platform network is able to be rapidly developed at low cost as its structure enables researchers from across disciplines and countries, to quickly, and informally, co-work on common SDG related research problems. Its capabilities are continuously being developed by its partners, with ongoing efforts exploring the potential of combining AI/ML and Citizen Science (Fortson et al., 2024) for the collection of building data, such as in the Colouring Dresden initiative (Danke et al., 2024). The algorithms and methods used in the study will be published and shared for reproduction and improvement in collaboration with other CCRP research partners. Another future development of the platform network is to allow for the easier deployment of instances while guaranteeing robustness between the versions. A database-based web deployment structure is being evaluated, combined with a plugin architecture, to facilitate the maintenance and updating of the core repository and enable seamless integration of each countries' platform. New open building datasets that are widely available at a large scale, such as the EUBUCCO, the Digital Building Stock Model (Florio et al., 2023), and global initiatives such as Overture Maps (OMF, 2025), provide an optimal basis for establishing platforms in countries where building footprints are not available, thereby accelerating the dissemination of the platform.

Data and Software Availability

All code and data are released under open licences. CCRP core platform code, and additional country specific code, are released under a GNU General Public License via GitHub and is available here <https://github.com/colouring-cities>. CCRP building attribute datasets are released via individual international platforms under an Open Data Commons Open Database

License, and the CCRP Open Manual released on GitHub under an MIT License.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they did not use any generative AI tools to generate scientific content, research data or substantial conclusions when preparing this manuscript. Only for the improvement of language, grammar and sentence structure, DeepL and duck.ai were used.

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